

Public Debt and Effect of Indian Economy

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Introduction

The public debt is one of the important crisis in India as well as World. The Central and State Governments are faced lot of financial crisis in recent decades. The level of public debt is increased in international, national and state level in different countries after the financial crisis in 2008. There is functional relationship between public debt and economic development in positive and negative relation are indicated by economist and policy makers. Whenever increasing more public debt is retard investment and economic growth. Huge size of public debt is impact on increase inflation, deficit of government budget and balance of payment problems, interest rate and budget deficit. It leads to socio-economic and political conditions are changes taking place. The repayment of interest rate to public debt is biggest problem in India. The Union Government has been spent one-third of total revenue as interest payment to external and internal sources.

The percentage of total public debt to GDP of the Central Government has gone up from 45 percent in 1980-81 to 95 percent in 2022-23. But external debt to GDP has been decreasing from 10 percent to 3 percent. After the new economic policy 1991 introduced, external debt has shown consistently a declining trend. The combined total public debt has shown an increasing trend from 1980-81 to 1991-92 due to fiscal stress and high primary deficits. The debt position was slightly improved during 1992-93 to 1996-97, because of the major structural reforms were undertaken in 1991-92 to tackle the balance of payment crisis faced (RBI, Status Paper of Public Debt, 2015). According to Economic Survey (2023) pointed out that public debt-to-GDP ratio has modest rise in the past years. The public debt is stable and low currency and interest rate risks. The total net liabilities of union government have reached to 95.1 percent due to domestic currency in End-March 2021. But external debt accounted for 5.0 percent, it implies that the low currency risk and volatility in the international capital markets. Public debt in India is primarily

contracted at fixed interest rates, with floating internal debt constituting only 1.7 percent of GDP in End-March 2021. The debt portfolio is insulated from interest rate volatility.

Objectives of the Paper

The objective of this study is to investigate the linkages between public debt and effect in Indian economy during 1990-91 to 2022-23. The first section deals with introduction. The second section presents a brief review of the theoretical perspective of public debt. The third section examines the trends and growth rates of public debt and effect in India. The fourth section gives the summary findings, conclusions.

Research Methodology and Data Base

This study is based on secondary data. It is collected from various published and unpublished sources of central and state government documents. The government documents were collected from Reserve Bank of India, Status Paper of Public Debt from 2015 to 2022, RBI State Budgets and India Economy Dataset, Data from Ministry of Finance, Government of India. The study periods covered from 1990-91 to 2022-23. The simple percentage and average were used to calculate the public debt and effect in India.

Theories of Public Debt

In 18th century, public debt was favoured by economists. They had great faith in the role of state in economic activities. They stated that the favourable attitude towards public debt was a part of mercantilist doctrine. In 19th and 20th Century, public debt was condemned by early classical economists. They lack of faith in the role of state in economic activities. David Hume, Adam Smith and David Ricardo stated that the consequences of public debt. They opposed to public debt and public expenditure is wasteful and unproductive. David Hume opposed public debt. He stated that nations once began to borrow, would be unable to resist, until they reached the point of bankruptcy. Adam Smith stated that once the sovereign started to borrow. His political power was increased because he was no longer dependent on tax exactions. Borrowing encouraged the sovereign to wage needless wars.

Ricardo noted that the national debt as most terrible scourges. It was to trouble a nation. Malthus, Mill, Sidgwick and Cairnes pointed that the consequence of public debt. Malthus noted that the material debt is not evil. Those who live on the interest from the national debt, like statesmen, soldiers and sailors contribute powerfully to distribution and demand. They ensure that effective consumption to necessary to give the proper stimulus to production. The debt created is not a great evil. Keynes stated that the modern theory of public debt is a compensation

of the economics depression. The economic irregularity created by the Great Depression in 1930s. He was developed the new theory of public debt. The classical theory of public debt assumed full employment and unproductiveness of public expenditure.

AH Hansen the advocate modern fiscal theory. He said that public debt is an essential means of increasing employment. It is become an instrument of economic policy today. The modern theory of public debt is alarmed with macro-economic variables and not with individual utilities. According to modern economist external debt is regarded as burden. Repayment of principal and interest to foreign countries are entailed, such repayments involves a transfer of real goods and services from the debtor to the creditor country in payment of interest and principal amount.

Public Debt in Global Perspective

United Nation addressed the high cost of debt and the mounting risk of debt distress is utmost importance in the World. Developing countries has borrow high debt burdens and require increased liquidity during times of crisis. Liquidity crisis risks turning into a debt crisis. The UN Secretary-General António Guterres presented the report that world of debt, growing burden to global prosperity. This five-fold overflow in public debt leads to tackle the mounting crisis affecting developing countries after 2000. It is warning global public debt reached an all-time high of \$92 trillion in 2022.

Economic Survey (2023) noted that India's debt is lower than global average. This Debt-to-GDP ratio is lower compared to major countries in the World. The global average debt-to-GDP ratio is 248 percent for all the countries. United States of America, England (UK), France, Japan and China has 264 percent, 257 percent, 345 percent, 426 percent and 295 percent, respectively. But, India has lowest debt-to-GDP ratio at 170 percent. IMF has projected that India will slow down for 2023. Cumulative impact of adverse shocks, aggressive and synchronous monetary policy tightening will lead to a moderation in growth. Banking sector turmoil in the US and the European Union (EU) has resulting in tightening of financial conditions could hamper the growth prospects.

Growth Trend of Public Debt in India

During first and second Five-Year Plans periods, public debt to GDP has increased from 30 percent in 1950-51 to 36 percent in 1960-61, remaining until 1964-65. Government borrowing has to finance public sector investment. Another problem was inability to generate public savings required financing to public sector investments. In 1965, government enforced a suspension the plan from 1966 to 68 due to economic recession. During second phase, government indebtedness

has declined sharply to 26.8 percent of GDP till 1975. During Third phase, the debt to GDP ratio has increased from 37.6 percent in 1980-81 to 45 percent in 1984-85 and further to 56.7 percent in 1990-91. The fiscal expansion and the sharp increase in primary and revenue deficits at central and state levels in 1980. It was rapid increase in debt-GDP ratio. Fiscal imbalance has caused macroeconomic imbalance and creating a crisis in 1991. During fourth phase, public debt began with fiscal containment was short-lived. The inability to contain government expenditures and declining tax-GDP ratio at the central level. It leads to the sharp increase in government indebtedness. It bringing to the serious questions of debt sustainability and solvency. The high and increasing volume of debt raised serious questions of stability and sustainability and dampening effect on economic growth. Much borrowing is undertaken to finance current expenditures of the central and state governments. It does not generate direct or indirect returns to the government to meet debt-servicing obligations. Vicious cycle creates imbalance between savings and investments and spills over into balance of payments problem. Debt is supportable as long as the interest rate is lower than the growth rate of the economy.

Source: RBI Hand Book of Statistics on Indian Economy (2022) GDP means GDP at market price. Total liabilities comprising (i) public debt (ii) other liabilities, Public debt comprising External debt and internal liabilities debt, other liabilities include (i) National Small Saving Funds (ii) State Provident Fund (iii) Other accounts such as special deposits (iv) Reserve funds.

The percentage share of public debt to GDP is increased from 32.57 percent in 1990-91 to 90.90 percent in 2020-21. From 1990-91 to 2008-09, there is slight increase in public debt to GDP ratio. It has increased double size of public debt to GDP from 87 percent in 2014-15 to 90.90 percent in 2020-21. It means increase internal public debt in the country. Out of that,

internal public debt to GDP ratio is increased from 27.04 percent in 1990-91 to 84.70 percent in 2020-21. It implies that the three times increased in internal public debt ratio. The source of internal public debt is like RBI, LIC, Other Public Sector Companies and other State Governments. External debt to GDP ratio is declined 5.53 percent in 1990-91 to 5.40 percent in 2020-21. It is fluctuated light remaining 5 percent from external sources like World Bank, IMF, Asian Development Bank. Government of India has collected from Indian internal public debt sources like LIC, Public and private sector companies.

Table 1: Debt on the Indian Government during 2011-12 to 2020-21

Year	Amount (in crore)	As percentage of GDP
2011-12	5917279	67.7
2012-13	6655685	66.9
2013-14	7566773	67.4
2014-15	8334826	66.8
2015-16	9475272	68.8
2016-17	10524777	68.4
2017-18	11702891	68.5
2018-19	12982467	68.7
2019-20	14992765	73.7
2020-21(RE)	17346517	87.8

Source: RBI Hand Book of Statistics on Indian Economy (2022) GDP means GDP at market price. Total liabilities comprising (i) public debt (ii) other liabilities, Public debt comprising External debt and internal liabilities debt, other liabilities include (i) National Small Saving Funds (ii) State Provident Fund (iii) Other accounts such as special deposits (iv) Reserve funds.

Public debt has been increased from Rs. 59,17,279 crores in 2011-12 to Rs. 173,46,517 crores in 2020-21. The percentage share has been increased from 68 percent to 88 percent. Nearly 20 percent of debt has been increased over 10 years. There is increase in public spending and expending economic activities in India. On the other hand, tax revenue has been reduced over the years. The total liabilities of central government have been increased from Rs. 62,42,520 crores in 2014-15 to Rs. 1,20,78,718 crores in 2020-21. Public debt has been increased from Rs. 51,04,675 crores in 2014-15 to Rs. 105,23,209 crores in 2020-21. In terms of percentage, it has increased from 82 percent to 87.12 percent in the same period.

The percentage of internal debt has been increased from Rs. 3400710 crores in 2011-12 to Rs. 9908380 crores in 2020-21. In terms of percentage, it has been increased from 76 percent to 82 percent in the same period. The amount of external debt has been increased from Rs. 366384 crores in 2014-15 to Rs. 614829 crores in 2020-21. In terms of percentage, it has been declined

from 5.87 percent to 5.01 percent in the same period. In India, the majority of public debt has been borrowed which internal sources from India, particularly from the internal debt like RBI, LIC, NABARD, state governments, public sector banks, private sector banks, marketable securities, national small savings, state provided fund, deposits from public.

The 14 Prime Ministers of India has borrowed total loan of Rs 55 lakh crore in 67 years. In 2004, when Manmohan Singh's government total debt was Rs 17 lakh crore. It increased more than three times to Rs 55 lakh crore in 2014. The average debt of every Indian at that time was Rs. 42000. In 2014-23, PM Narendra Modi has tripled the debt of Rs.100 lakh crore. In 2023, the total debt has increased to Rs 155 lakh crore. Indian has a debt of more than 1 lakh rupees. Debt has increased by 181 percent during 2014 to 23.

Source: RBI Hand Book of Statistics on Indian Economy (2022) GDP means GDP at market price.

In 2014-15, India's foreign debt was Rs 31 lakh crore. But, 2023, India's foreign debt has increased to Rs 50 lakh crore. In 2014, the BJP promised it would reduce the debt, but in 2014-23, the debt has increased. Since 2014, Modi government has taken a total loan of Rs 19 lakh crore from abroad. During 2005 to 2013, the United Progressive Alliance government has taken a foreign loan Rs 21 lakh crore. In 2005, the country's foreign debt was 10 lakh crores, which increased to 31 lakh crores in 2013. Means, foreign debt increased by Rs 21 lakh crore in 9 years. During 2014 to 2022, the foreign debt increased from Rs 33 lakh crore to Rs 50 lakh crore,

the foreign debt increased by Rs 19 lakh crore. IMF expects India's general government fiscal deficit to improve to 8.9 percent of GDP in 2023 from an estimated 9.6 percent of GDP in 2022.

Economic Effect on Indian Economy

FRBM Act 2003 mandates Debt Ceilings of 60 percent for general government and 40 percent for the Central government. Government debt has increase due to the private sector is recovering its balance sheet after a phase of over-borrowing. Government expenditure in infrastructure and other capital asset has building helps crowd in private investment. The general government interest payments as a percentage of revenues indicate debt affordability. It indicates a low level of debt affordability. The increase public debt-GDP ratio is higher than different Finance Commission's long-term debt to GDP ratio. This rising growth trends has been caused by expansion in the size of government activities in India.

Market borrowing dated securities has been increased from Rs. 404050 crores in 2015-16 to Rs 775772 crores in 2021-22. In terms of percentage, share has been declined from 76 percent to 49 percent. The second highest financing small savings. It is increased ten told size from Rs. 52465 crores in 2015-16 to Rs. 591524 crores in 2021-22. In term of percentage, share has been increased from 10 percent to 37.2 percent in the same period. The third highest borrowing short term borrowing, it is increased from Rs. 50693 crores to Rs: 100000 crores in the same period. In terms of percentage, share has been increased from 9.5 percent in 2015-16 to 11.2 percent in 2021-22. It has declined to 6.3 percent in 2021-22. The total fiscal deficit of the central government has been increased from Rs: 532792 crores in 2015-16 to Rs.1591089 crores in 2021-22. The percentage share of fiscal deficit to GDP has been increased from 3.9 percent in 2015-16 to 6.9 percent in 2021-22. The fiscal deficit has been increased to 3 percent over the six years, Union government has been implemented FRBM Act 2003, for reduction of fiscal deficit in India.

Source: RBI Hand Book of Statistics on Indian Economy (2022) GDP means GDP at market price.

The financing needs of governments have been rising as countries strive to bring COVID-19 under control leading to governments' debt reaching record high levels, globally. Larger recourse to market borrowing was the common trend across countries. While the cost of borrowings declined in general, reflecting the impact of quantitative easing stance of the central banks and the low policy interest rates, significant increase in risk aversion and resultant preference for government securities (G-sec) led to a larger demand for these securities since 2020-21. In line with the global trend, Government of India (GoI) also responded to the pandemic challenges and increased government expenditure on health and social sector. At the same time, revenue receipts declined due to cliff effects of the pandemic on economic activity. Consequently, fiscal deficit widened necessitating an increase in the size of the borrowing programme significantly during 2020-21 and 2021-22 in order to render countercyclical fiscal policy support and provide targeted support to segments deeply hit by the pandemic (Economic Survey 2023).

The high proportion of revenue going towards interest payments reduces the funds for developmental activities. In addition, it reduces the capacity of the government to respond to the next economic shock/crisis. Rise in primary deficit and deterioration in interest rate growth differential, since 2019 cast doubts on debt sustainability of India. High growth can support and

help reduce a high public debt. This capacity to support public debt is seen in how high the interest rate-growth differential. The increase debt affordability, tax buoyancy are needs to be improved along with expansion of the tax base. Low currency risk and volatility in the international capital markets. High volume of borrowing is to finance large fiscal deficits continues serious concern. Capital expenditure is raises aggregate supply as well as aggregate demand. As a result, the budget's focus on capex means the additional spending announced is stoke inflationary pressures. Slow fiscal consolidation process in the wake of the Covid-19 pandemic could major economic shocks. Fiscal consolidation is to arrest rapid growth of internal indebtedness.

Table 2: Outstanding Central Government Debt - Other Liabilities (Amount in Crore)

Years	Small Savings/ National Small Savings Fund	State Provident Funds	Special Sec. Issued to OMCs, FCI	Special deposits of Non- Govt. Provident Fund	Other Items	Total (4+5+6)	Bearing interest
1990-91	52899	8871	0	33588	11749	45336	1887
1995-96	103611	17786	0	65712	26297	92009	4452
2000-01	66633	41721	385	103866	39769	144020	1756
2005-06	414552	66262	26611	118257	60609	205477	12649
2010-11	568614	111947	182123	108260	58778	349161	473
2011-12	582011	122751	172091	102636	58877	333604	2392
2012-13	597737	133672	166329	102171	58400	326901	5283
2013-14	629184	143425	166328	102662	46431	315421	8226
2014-15	646895	155334	162828	103597	49205	315630	9872
2015-16	701369	167193	162828	103597	53375	319800	13842
2016-17	751199	184938	162828	102928	56101	321857	6668
2017-18	805685	200737	162828	102671	59134	324633	8328
2018-19	892689	216795	162828	102014	61777	326619	13006
2019-20	932964	228430	162828	101466	169496	433790	-13792
2020-21	754795	246944	162828	100702	182950	446479	17004

Source: RBI Hand Book of Statistics on Indian Economy (2022) GDP means GDP at market price.

The total outstanding liabilities of the central government has been increased from Rs. 45,336 crore in 1990-91 to Rs.4,44,479 crore in 2020-21. The total outstanding liabilities is increased to 10 times over 30 years. It is burden to the central government. Small saving, national small savings found has increased from Rs. 52,895 crore in 1990-91 to Rs. 7,54,795 crore in 2020-21. The small saving is increased to 14 times, the saving habits have been increased among the public in India. The majority in India have saving habits increased. The actual state provided fund has been increased from Rs. 8,871 crore in 1990-91 to RS 2,46,944 crore in 2020-21. The SPF has been increased to 28 times the different state government have been collated found in terms of SPF during 30 years. The provident fund would be repayable after certain period of time this burden also increased among different states in India. The recommendation of the 14th Finance Commission (FC) to exclude states from the National Small Savings Fund (NSSF) financing facility (barring Delhi, Madhya Pradesh, Kerala and Arunachal Pradesh), market borrowings of states have been increasing over the last few years. The share of market borrowings in financing GFD of states consequently rose to 85.1 percent in 2021- 22 (BE) from 77.8 per cent in 2020-21 (RE).

Summary and Conclusions

Public debt to GDP ratio has increased from 32.57 percent in 1990-91 to 91.10 percent in 2020-21. It noted that the three-times increase during three decades. The internal debt to GDP ratio is second highest borrowed from internal sources of the country. The internal debt to GDP ratio has increased from 27 percent to 85 percent in the same period. It implies that the majority

of internal borrowers are LIC, SBI, and Other nationalised banks, NABARD, RBI and other state governments in India. The external debt to GDP ratio is meagre percentage in three decades. It is more or less stagnant in the economic system. Total liabilities to GDP ratio has been increased little from 55.22 percent to 59.20 percent during the same period.

The amount of public debt has increased from Rs. 59,17,279 crores in 2011-12 to Rs. 173,46,517 crores in 2020-21. The percentage share of public debt to GDP in India has increased from 68 percent in 2011-12 to 88 percent in 2020-21. Nearly 20 percent of debt has increased over 10 years. There is increase in public spending and expending economic activities in India. On the other hand, tax revenue has been reduced over the years.

The total liabilities of central government have increased from Rs. 62, 42,520 crores in 2014-15 to Rs. 1, 20, 78,718 crores in 2020-21. Public debt has increased from 82 percent to 87.12 percent in the same period. The percentage of internal debt has increased from 76 percent to 82 percent in the same period. The amount of external debt has declined from 5.87 percent to 5.01 percent in the same period.

In India, the majority of public debt has borrowed which internal sources from India, particularly from the internal debt like RBI, LIC, NABARD, state governments, public sector banks, private sector banks, marketable securities, national small savings, state provided fund, deposits from public.

The internal debt has increased from Rs. 3230622 crores to Rs. 9908380 crores in the same period. The amount of external debt has increased from Rs. 170088 crores in 2011-12 to Rs. 388472 crores in 2020-21. The amount of other liabilities has decline from Rs.1116542 crores to Rs.1782167 crores in the same period. It implies that the national small saving fund, state provident fund, other all major used.

The short-term debt to GDP ratio of the union government has 3.6 percent to 6.4 percent during 10 years. Nearly, it is increased to 2.8 percent. It is implies that the short-term bills, treasurer bills, 184 days bills and 364 days bills incurred in the short-term debt.

Market borrowing dated securities has declined from 76 percent to 49 percent during 2004-15 to 2020-21. The second highest financing small savings. In term of percentage, share has increased from 10 percent to 37.2 percent. The third highest borrowing short term borrowing has increased from 9.5 percent in 2015-16 to 11.2 percent in 2021-22. The total fiscal deficit to GDP of the central government has increased from 3.9 percent in 2015-16 to 6.9 percent in 2021-22.

The fiscal deficit has increased to 3 percent over the six years, Union government has implemented FRBM Act 2003, for reduction of fiscal deficit in India.

The actual gross market borrowing has increased from Rs. 100206 crore in 2000-01 to Rs. 1360116 crore in 2020-21. The actual gross market borrowing has increased 12 times over 20-year period. The main reason public spending on different sectors have increased. the union government have borrowing finds from market like open, market, securities, 182 day insure bills, market loans, others.

The total outstanding liabilities of the central government has increased from Rs. 45,336 crore in 1990 -91 to Rs.4,44,479 crore in 2020-21. The total outstanding liabilities is increased to 10 times over 30 years. It is burden to the central government. It would repay within certain period of time. Out of that, small saving, national small savings found has increased from Rs. 52,895 crore in 1990-91 to Rs. 7,54,795 crore in 2020-21. The small saving is increased to 14 times, the saving habits have increased among the public in India. The majority in India have saving habits increased.

The securities small saving fund is the top most debt in India. The amount has increased from Rs. 193,516 crore in 2000-01 to Rs. 13,32,652 crore in 2020-21. The securities small saving fund is increased to 6 times during 20 years. The second highest outstanding is market loans; the total market loans has increased from Rs. 4,66,562 crore in 2000-01 to Rs. 78,59,505 crore in 2020-21. The total market loan is increased 17 times. The market loans are increased due to open market operation, primary to secondary market, T-bills in India. The market loans have increased due to economic activities.

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